

Defying machines: an interactive demo of artificial intelligence and collaborative robotics

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Abstract—This short contribution witnesses the commitment of the research group of Mechatronics and Industrial Robotics of the Polytechnic University of Marche in disseminating the basic concepts of artificial intelligence and collaborative robotics towards the general public of non-academics involved in the European level event Sharper – the European Researchers’ Night. To this purpose, a dedicated demo has been set up involving themes of artificial intelligence, computer vision and collaborative robotics, with the aim inviting people to test the logical capabilities of an artificial system through a common board game.

Index Terms—collaborative robotics, dual-arm robot, artificial intelligence, computer vision

I. INTRODUCTION

The SHARPER [1] project was created in response to the need to value the figure of researchers and their role in society. To achieve this goal, the central idea of Sharper’s promoters has been, since 2013, to interpret the Night as a festive opportunity to share with the general public the passions that animate researchers in their work by discovering that these passions are common to everyone. While the Night is an opportunity for engagement and discovery, it is also an example of how research dissemination must be an act of responsibility. An engagement to emphasize the cultural and political role that researchers and citizens together can and should play in social growth. In this spirit, the researchers of the Mechatronics and Industrial Robotics group of the Polytechnic university of Marche have taken the opportunity to introduce their research topics, centered on industrial and collaborative robotics, to the city of Ancona through a demonstrator conceive on the purpose.

The key idea of collaborative robotics, as well known, is that of setting up human-centered automated processes by allowing the humans to engage the robot workspace with an acceptable level of risk [2], [3]. Aside pushing robot constructors to produce cobots (*collaborative robots*) increasingly reliable in their safety features, this tendency is also challenging the researchers to develop safety-centered control strategies and workspace monitoring paradigms capable of keeping the labourers safe while performing their duties [4]. Although this common objective, the distrust of these technologies is still widespread [5]. To overcome this bias, this project wants to

invite people to share the workspace of a small cobot (namely the dual arm YuMi by ABB) by asking them to challenge the machine to a game of *Connect 4*, the well known board game.

Besides introducing cobots, the setup of the demo allowed to present some crucial technologies, necessary to make the whole system work, and of uttermost importance in the field of modern automation [6], [7]. In particular the demo gave a chance to talk about the concept of workspace sensing through computer vision, and the artificial intelligence necessary for both interpret the information coming from sensors (i.e., a simple webcam) and to teach the robot what move to make in response to human players. Also, the the system is an excellent example of how challenging the integration of singularly simple technologies (at least from the perspective of common industrial practice) can be, especially when interaction with a human operator, which is unpredictable by nature, is involved.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE DEMONSTRATOR

As mentioned, the system has been set up with a dual arm collaborative robot, namely the YuMi by ABB. The mechanical arrangement of the demo is quite simple (see Fig. 1). The robot was equipped with a color webcam capable of framing the work space in front of it. The game board was placed in front of the robot, in the space accessible by both

Fig. 1. Layout of the demo.

Fig. 2. Functional scheme of the control arrangement.

arms of the machine and the human player sitting in front of it. The fiches that the cobot is asked to manipulate are piled in a peripheral region of the workspace. From a motion control point of view, the task operated by the cobot has been programmed offline through a fixed sequence of motions. Starting from its home configuration, the right arm of the robot picks one of the piled fiches grasping it on its circumference. Such grasp is not feasible to thuck the plastic disc into the board, thus the robot performs a regrasp passing the fiche to the left hand, which grabs it from the two faces. While the left arm moves its payload to the assigned column of the board, the right one goes back in its home configuration. At the end of the move, also the left arm is homed. The sequence is repeated at each passage of the game.

The control arrangement is shown in Fig. 2. Both the webcam and the robot controller are connected to an external computer, whose tasks are mainly three: to receive the visual information coming from the camera to perceive the move executed by the human player, to run the artificial intelligence needed to pick up the subsequent move of the artificial player, and to command the proper set of motions to YuMi needed to perform the appropriate response. For the sake of simplicity, the image processing and the communication job performed by the computer have been developed in Matlab, while the artificial player runs on a parallel Python thread.

Being the moves executed in sequence, the only piece of information needed by the artificial intelligence to plan its response is the column in which the human player slipped the fiche. Such input is extrapolated through the webcam the robot is provided with by means of a dedicated *Convolutional Neural Network* (CNN) developed and trained in Matlab environment. This has been done for two reasons. Firstly, the workspace

Fig. 3. (a) Perceived image of the workspace (lab test) with original shape of the board and (b) processed region of interest.

Fig. 4. (a) Graph of the YOLO CNN used for fiches detection; (b) example set of labeled images used for machine learning.

framed by the webcam is poorly structured as visible in Fig. 3 (a) (variable light conditions and, above all, randomness of the environment around and behind the board, which is not opaque because of the holes themselves that allow the game). In second place, the geometric repeatability of the images (due to the fixed geometric layout) allowed to produce a very reliable set of images feasible for the *Supervised Learning* of the CNN by simply extrapolating a constant region of interest from the captured frames (see Fig. 3 (b)). In particular, it has been chosen to use a pre-trained YOLO (You Look Only Once) detector whose graph is reported in Fig. 4 (a). The learning process thus involved only the first and last layers of the network. The data set used as ground truth has been manually labelled (as shown in Fig. 4 (b)). Actually, the labelling process has been semi-automated being the position of each column and row of the board fixed within each frame.

III. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The document shows the demo developed by the research team of the Polytechnic University of Marche to take part at the SHARPER festive event, organized and designed to spread the importance of the scientific research (as well as the of the social role of researchers) towards the general audience. The demonstrator, basically a robotic artificial player for the board game Connect 4, involved the integration of many technologies (collaborative robotics, artificial intelligence, computer vision) of paramount importance to pursue the dictates of the Industry 4.0 paradigm.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Sharper 30.09.22," <https://www.sharper-night.it/>.
- [2] R. Galin and R. Meshcheryakov, "Automation and robotics in the context of industry 4.0: the shift to collaborative robots," in *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 537, no. 3. IOP Publishing, 2019, p. 032073.
- [3] F. Vicentini, "Terminology in safety of collaborative robotics," *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 63, p. 101921, 2020.
- [4] F. Neri, C. Scoccia, L. Carbonari, G. Palmieri, M. Callegari, L. Tagliavini, G. Colucci, and G. Quaglia, "Dynamic obstacle avoidance for omnidirectional mobile manipulators," in *The International Conference of IFToMM ITALY*. Springer, 2022, pp. 746–754.
- [5] T. Kopp, M. Baumgartner, and S. Kinkel, "Success factors for introducing industrial human-robot interaction in practice: an empirically driven framework," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 112, no. 3, pp. 685–704, 2021.
- [6] E. Andrade Borges, "Exploring computer vision for human awareness in human-cobot interactions," 2021.
- [7] P. Ammann and P. Burkhalter, "Artificial intelligence in practical use (case study)," *The case centre org*, pp. 1–28, 2021.